

Clinico-Radiological Findings of Acute Pain Abdomen in Pediatrics Age Group at Tertiary Care Hospital in North-Eastern Region**Debbarma Tanusri¹, Debbarma Kaushik², Debbarma Ripan³, Mog Chanda⁴, Debbarma Pranab⁵**¹Assistant Professor, Dept of Radiodiagnosis, AGMC & GBP Hospital, Agartala, India²MD Paediatrics, MO, GR-III THS, IGM Hospital, Dept of Paediatrics, Agartala, India³Assistant Professor, Dept of Paediatrics, Agartala, AGMC & GBP Hospital, India⁴Assistant Professor, Dept of community Medicine, AGMC & GBP Hospital, Agartala, India⁵Associate Professor, Dept of Anatomy, AGMC & GBP Hospital, Agartala, India

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Abstract:

Acute non-traumatic abdominal pathologies in the pediatric population depend on the age of the patients and symptoms. The common complaint in pediatric emergency departments (ED), abdominal pain is sometimes hard to assess in ill children due to the variation of pain degree, the difficulty in describing it, and being localized to the abdomen. Although most children with abdominal pain have a self-limiting course, some critical medical and surgical emergencies may occur in the ED. The aim of the present case series is to describe the varied imaging manifestations of acute pain abdomen etio-pathology. Also to provide some information for physicians in pediatric emergency departments, with the age factors and several causes of non-traumatic acute abdominal pain. Case presentation This is a retrospective review of imaging findings in ten patients with intra-operative proven case of various etiology in case of acute pain abdomen in our institute from February 2023 to February 2024. This article summarizes the imaging approach to pediatric patients with acute abdominal pathologies presenting to the emergency department. Herlyn warner Wunderlich's syndrome, duplication cyst, Acute appendicitis, inguinal Hernia, midgut volvulus, Hirschsprung disease, Wandering Spleen with Splenic Ischemia, intussusceptions were the cases. In conclusion, the etiologies of acute abdomen in children admitted to the emergency department vary depending on age. A complete history and detailed physical examination, as well as abdominal imaging examinations, could provide useful information for physicians in the emergency department to narrow the differential diagnosis of abdominal emergencies and give a timely treatment.

Keywords: Abdomen and GIT, Urogenital, hernia, pediatric, USG, MRI.

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Introduction

Acute non-traumatic abdominal pain is a common complaint in pediatric emergency departments. The differential diagnosis of acute abdominal pain depends on the age of the patient [1]. P Patients less than 2 years old are particularly a challenge because their symptoms are non-specific and may present with inconsolable crying, fussiness and lethargy.

Differential considerations are guided primarily by associated symptoms such as bilious emesis pointing to an upper gastrointestinal obstruction, or currant jelly stool pointing to a lower gastrointestinal pathology, namely intussusception [2] Herlyn-Werner-Wunderlich (HWW) syndrome is a very rare congenital anomaly of the urogenital tract resulting from maldevelopment of both Mullerian and Wolffian ducts. It is characterized by the triad of uterus didelphys, obstructed

hemivagina and ipsilateral renal agenesis. It generally presents at puberty shortly following menarche with the symptom of acute pelvic pain. Management of these cases is surgical and consists mainly of vaginoplasty with excision of the vaginal septum in order to release the obstruction and prevent the long term complication of recurrent pyocolpos and infertility. [3]

Intestinal malrotation is a major diagnostic challenge in children. Sometimes the prognostic significance of the findings from upper gastrointestinal tract examinations is unclear. A volvulus is a medical condition where the intestines twist upon themselves. This condition can occur at any age. However, it is more frequent in children and infants [4]. Acute appendicitis should always be considered in patients with right lower quadrant tenderness, particularly those with persistent pain

associated with fever and leukocytosis. The findings on radiographs are non-specific and almost never diagnostic. The most specific finding of an abdominal plain film is the presence of a calcified appendicolith (Figure 5); however, this is only present in less than 10% of patients [5] Wandering spleen is characterized by excessive mobility and migration of the spleen from its normal position in the left hypochondrium due to lack of fixation and unduly long splenic pedicle. Congenitally, wandering spleen is the result of failure of development of the gastrosplenic and lienorenal ligaments, which results in long splenic mesentery. The spleen develops in the dorsal mesogastrium, and through rotation of the gut it moves posterolaterally to the left. Fusion of the dorsal mesogastrium to the posterior abdominal wall and the left kidney forms the lienorenal ligament, which contains the tail of the pancreas and the splenic artery. Failure of fusion produces an abnormally long pedicle. [6]

Early diagnosis and treatment of hirschprung disease (HSD) are essential to prevent complications such as enterocolitis and colonic rupture, diagnosing or ruling out HSD presents significant challenges for physicians practicing in low and middle income countries. [7] Entric duplication cysts are uncommon congenital abnormalities arising anywhere along the GT. Their clinical presentations vary according to the site of duplication; ileum appears as the most commonly involved. [8]

Case findings: This is a retrospective review of imaging findings in ten patients with intraoperative diagnosed at our institute (a tertiary care hospital in northeastern India) between February 2023-February 2024. We present here the spectrum of imaging manifestations in these cases.

Case 1: Herlyn warner Wunderlich's syndrome: A 10 year's old female came with the history of acute pain abdomen during menstruation. On USG, Large pelvic mass lesion with complete duplication of uterine horns as well as duplication of cervix, vagina was noted. Empty right renal fossa was noted. Right hemi-vagina was distended with high echogenic collection due to obstructed vagina'. On CT angiography, empty right renal fossa with duplication of left ureter. Complete duplication of uterine horns as well as duplication of cervix, vagina were noted. Large hyperdense collection was seen in hemivagina. Well defined cystic lesion is seen between the bladder and vagina measuring approx. 1.75 cm x 1.2 cm. On MRI, hyperintense collection in hemivagina on T1WI, Duplication of uterine horns and Empty right renal fossa were noted. (Fig-1) So finally we diagnosed as a case of duplication of uterine horns with right renal agenesis, haematocolpos so features suggestive of Herlyn warner Wunderlich's syndrome. On OT,

Patient was relieved by aspirating the haematocolpos, around 200cc of blood mixed organized collection was obtained. The collection showed no growth.

Case 2: Left Sided Inguinal Hernia With Bilateral Hydrocele: A 3 months old baby came with swelling in the left inguinal region since 1 month which increases on crying. On Chest x-ray and abdominal x-ray were normal. On USG :A small defect was seen in the left inguinal area extending to the groin region which was non reducible and also reactive bilateral hydrocele were noted. Pt was operated and resolved.

Case 3: Large Duplication Cyst: Female baby of 14 days with history of large abdominal swelling. No history of fever was noted. On X-ray, large well defined radiolucent cystic lesion with collapsed bowel loops were noted..(Fig-)On USG, large well defined cystic lesion without any flow and peristalsis are noted. On CT A large well defined cystic lesion was noted. Contrast enhanced CT with oral contrast was given to delineate any communication with the bowel loops, but there was no communication with the loops. (Fig-2)

Case 4: Hirschprung Disease Causing Large Bowel Obstruction: A 4months old male child not passing stool for last 10 days and fever. Since birth no difficulty in passing stool and urine. On X ray & Barium enema, dilated bowel loops & inverse dilatation of recto-sigmoid ratio were noted. (Fig-3). On CT there was a inverse dilatation of recto-sigmoid ratio with large bowel obstruction. Patient was operated & was Uneventful postoperative. (Fig-3)

Case 5: Wandering Spleen with Splenic Ischemia: A 15 years old female came with weakness, on examination patient was on shock, her blood parameters were very low. On X ray, splenic shadow was absent in the left lumbar region. Bowel loops were normal. Abdominal USG and colour Doppler flow imaging revealed a 10 x 9 cm spleen with hypoechoic parenchyma situated antero-inferior to the left kidney in the left iliac fossa with tortuous, elongated splenic vessels with torsion & swirling sign of splenic vessels with absent flow in the splenic parenchyma were noted .Minimal perisplenic collection was also noted.

Contrast-enhanced CT of the abdomen revealed a 10 x 9 cm spleen in the left iliac fossa, with a long, tortuous pedicle, swirling sign, non-enhancing splenic vessels & without any splenic parenchymal enhancement S/O torsion with splenic parenchymal ischemia. Patient was done splenectomy. The patient's post-operative recovery was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on the 5th post-operative day.(Fig-4)

Case 6: Iliocolic Intussusceptions: A 6 months old baby came with history of acute abdominal pain at right lumbar area, excessive crying and passing of currant jelly red stool for 2 days. On barium meal flow through, claw sign was seen.

On Usg target sign i.e concentric alternating echogenic and hypoechoic bands are seen at right lumbar region. On CT, concentric alternating band bowel within bowel of terminal ilium protrudes to the colon are seen. (Fig-5)

Case 7: Midgut Volvulus: A 11 year’s old female presented with chief complaints of vomiting after food intake for last 6 months at surgery OPD. Routine blood investigation within normal limits .The patient is subsequently referred to Department of Radiology for ultrasonography, where she underwent USG, Barium study and CT.

On Barium meal study reveals cork-screw appearance of proximal jejunum with D-J flexure in right side. DJ junction is in right side of the vertebral column with abrupt beaking was noted.

Ultrasonography showed ‘whirlpool’ appearance with Inverse SMA-SMV relationship; Superior mesenteric artery is left and posterior to the superior mesenteric vein. Proximal dilation of duodenal loops with edematous wall thickening of malrotated loops. On Contrast CT study shows cork-screw like rotation of mesentery and bowel loops. Distended and edematous duodenal wall with Inverted SMA-SMV relationship was also noted. Patient was done splenectomy. The patient’s post-operative recovery was uneventful, and the patient was discharged on the 5th post-operative day. (Fig-6)

Case 8: Acute Appendicitis: A 6 year’s old male came with acute abdominal pain, nausea & vomiting. Pain also aggravates to the paraumbilical area. On X-ray Facecloth was seen in the right iliac fossa. On USG non peristaltic, dilated tubular, non-compressible with adjacent fat stranding & collection was seen in the right iliac fossa. Patient was Operated & Postoperative was uneventful..(Fig-7)

Figure 1: Herlyn warner wonderlich’s syndrome: CT & MRI showing two separate uterine horns (upper), hematocolpos & right renal agenesis

Figure 2: A- X ray abdomen showing large radiolucent cystic swelling occupying the abdomen

On CT (Lung, A& Soft tissue window, B) showing large cystic swelling occupying the abdomen & compressing the other bowel loops.

Figure 3: X-ray Abdomen showing the multiple dilated bowel loops On Barium enema shows inverse rectosigmoid ratio with dilated bowel loops, On CT scan showing dilated bowel loops features are cases of hirschsprung diseases

Figure 4: On Usg & CECT: Empty Splenic fossa with a well-defined ovoid soft tissue mass (Mean 49.69 HU) with non-enhancement on post contrast in comparison to liver, whorled appearance of splenic vessels seen in the left lower quadrant at the level of L 1 to L 3 vertebrae .Non enhancing spleen like structure with whorled appearance of splenic vessels involving left lower quadrant, Minimal ascites & endometrial collection.(Wandering spleen with infarction).

Figure 5: On post-operative: specimen showing Splenectomy of ischemic spleen

Figure 6: X ray shows the claw sign, On USG-target sign, on CT scan shows bowel within bowel appearance

Figure 7: A& B: Image-A and B -Barium meal study showing a cork-screw proximal jejunum, with the DJ-flexure never reaching the left side of the abdomen and right of the vertebral column

Figure 8: C& D, E: : Image A,B & C ;USG color and pulse Doppler with linear high frequency probe showing 'whirlpool' appearance .Inverted SMA-SMV relationship. Thick edematous wall of malrotated bowel loops. CECT whole abdomen study transverse image showing inverse SMA-SMV relationship with clockwise rotation of bowel loops

Figure 9: A transverse USG image of an inflamed appendix with collection in the lateral wall of the appendix & On CT Phlegmon formation was noted (Arrow heads)

Discussion

A volvulus can cause a blockage that may cut off blood flow usually due to a congenital disability called intestinal malrotation; this can occur in any part of the intestine without this condition present. Intestinal malrotation can make an infant more likely to develop a midgut volvulus and occurs in the first few weeks of life. A midgut volvulus is usually part of a vascular compromise in the intestinal mesentery in intestinal malrotation [9].

The absence or weakness of one or more of these suspensory ligaments may explain the congenital form of wandering spleen, which resulted from a problem in the fusion of the dorsal mesogastrum with the posterior abdominal wall during the second month of embryogenesis [10].

A recent study found that late diagnosis of Hirschsprung disease defined as diagnosis at or over 1 year of age, was associated with more complications. [11] New US signs are described according to the characteristics of the Enteric Duplication cysts, it contains the same multi-layered wall architecture as the normal GT, the sign five-layered cyst wall[^] is proposed.

It corresponds to the innermost hyperechoic mucosa, hypoechoic muscularis mucosa, hyperechoic submucosa, hypoechoic muscularis propria and the outermost hyperechoic serosa. Identification of all five layers in a cyst is pathognomonic of EDC. However, this sign is difficult to demonstrate and needs expertise and high resolution US. [12]

The major concern of OHVIRAS was to relieve obstruction and prevent recurrence by hemihysterectomy rather than preserving the uterus which would have been the preferred option in most cases as they present early in life. [13] Improved accuracy and the development of definitive guidelines for the use of ultrasound in the diagnosis of suspected appendicitis would provide surgeons with improved decision-making ability and reduce the need to expose children to the

potentially harmful effects of CT, particularly in nonpaediatric health facilities. [14]

Conclusions

As observed in literature and our case series, Acute pain abdomen is truly a great masquerade. Awareness of the imaging manifestation of acute pain abdomen is therefore important and should be considered as a possible cause of any diseases in an appropriate clinical setting. Early diagnosis of these cases will aid in the appropriate management of these patients the differential considerations of acute nontraumatic abdominal pain in the pediatric patients presenting to the emergency department depends on the age of the patient and the associated symptoms.

The choice of the imaging modality is highly dependent on the suspected etiology. Ultrasound plays a pivotal role in assessing these patients because it allows real-time imaging assessment and does not involve ionizing radiation. MRI, although highly sensitive in detecting much pathology, is of little use in emergency situations due to prolonged imaging time, which, if improved, has promising future implications.

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